

Experiences and Challenges of College Students in Online and Distance Learning, Philippines

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Using quantitative-qualitative research methods, this study tries to describe the college student experiences and preferences in online and distance learning in the different public and private state universities and colleges (SUCs) in Camarines Sur. Specifically, this study: (1) recorded and analyzed the experiences of high school and senior high school students on online and distance learning; (2) identified the challenges they encountered; (3) determined their coping mechanism of students to deal with identified challenges; (4) described the initial support given by parents, and instructors to address these challenges; and (5) assessed the college students' preferences on online and distance learning.

The main respondents of the study were 1,225 college student learners of public and private SUCs in Camarines Sur using online learning system. Different schools were distributed to cater different responses from the varied scenarios as challenges experienced by students in online and distance learning. Online interview was also conducted to clarify some responses and validate some data for interpretation.

Findings revealed that there are commonly varied of causes of poor attendance of college students in online classes. These are due to poor internet connectivity, disappointments/loss of motivation, instructor's factor, due to difficulty in learning and due to other causes such as lack of financial support, household errands, geographical location and weather condition, unannounced blackout/power interruptions and poor mobile phone gadget/services. Some other causes are also true to the challenges on attendance and punctuality of students. Other challenges are lack of discipline/focus, difficulty in completion of modules, forgetfulness/poor time management. Meanwhile, another challenge in online and distance learning is how do students acquire knowledge and skills. Among other challenges are poor assessment, emotional state, disappointment and lack of focus, negative attitudes towards online and distance learning and the need for instructors' input.

In order to cope with these challenges this study, this study analyzed how students coped along digital divide, data limit, poor connectivity, learners' inefficiency. For digital divide among their strategies are extending support to disadvantaged students. As to data limit, student learned to sustain resources by finding an extra job, saving/thrifting allowances, managing usage of load, connecting wifi with family and friends or reconnecting to piso net, seeking financial help from family, outsourcing learning materials, and switching to internet providers. For those students with poor internet connectivity, some of their strategies are relocating, seeking help from others and informing excuses from instructors and managing time when strong signal is most available. Students woke up earlier or slept too late at night to avail of the internet. Learners' inefficiency are described along indiscipline, unmotivated and worsening health issue due to prolonged exposure to radiation. Among their strategies are developing self-discipline, time management, motivating oneself, setting priorities, goal setting and engaging in some leisure activities to do some exercise or relaxation to distress.

Initial support extended by instructors as experienced by student-respondents are communicating with them, giving guidance and assistance, providing materials and recorded lectures, giving special considerations and catering individual needs. Meanwhile, parents initial support are imposing discipline and providing guidance and moral support, giving financial support, and assistance, goal setting, encouragement and motivation. Finally, it was found out the students' preference in online and distance learning is weak considering those challenges which is rooted to poor internet connectivity and other interplaying factors like readiness and negative attitudes towards online learning, among others.

It can be concluded that there are an interplay of different challenges of students which affects their preference in online and distance learning. This is also reflected on their attendance and punctuality in online classes. Major causes of students' challenges are poor internet connectivity, instructors' factor and learner's inefficiency. Although most of them are struggling with this new style of learning, students also applied varied coping mechanism strategies to overcome these challenges. It can be concluded that support from teachers and parents are important in these trying times. College students still needs teachers' input to enhance their knowledge and develop their skills. Meanwhile, their level of satisfaction on online and distance learning is found moderately weak.

It is recommended that these identified challenges may serve as input in designing online curriculum and alternative program for students facing difficulty in online and distance learning. In terms of poor internet connectivity, the institution shall devise internet assistance programs that would cater their students' needs and difficulties in cooperation with the local government unit

and other funding agencies. Dissemination of learning materials may be intensified however, while developing the value of social and professional responsibility and embracing the new normal among students is essential. Students may be given series of orientation before online class started. A clear classroom policy may be reflected in the syllabus and may be revisited based on the background of students. Set expectations explicit and have the consequences flexible and specific in order to develop students' sense of discipline. Classroom management may also be adjusted to this new style of learning without sacrificing the causes for continual absenteeism and drop outs. Communication and support system may be extended with leniency but the gap between traditional face to face instruction preferences and readiness to online and distance learning may be bridged.

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CHEPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 is a global public health emergency that has affected practically every country and community on the planet, including education. Hatip (2020) suggested that the impact of the learning transition during the covid-19 pandemic into the new normal age is significant. It makes no distinctions based on nationality, ethnicity, disability status, age, or gender (UNICEF, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has wreaked havoc on education systems around the world, affecting almost 1.6 billion students across 190 countries and continents. As a third-world country, the Philippines is significantly more afflicted by the pandemic. During these unique circumstances, Ali (2020) highlighted the essence of continual learning, while Peters, et al (2020) chronicled student experiences.

Strict isolation measures, the closure of schools and workplaces, and loss of income to many families has had, and will continue to have, significant negatives impacts upon education, health, and wellbeing (Giannini, 2020). Students' responses to learning in the early COVID-19 Pandemic were studied by Wargadinata, Maimunah, Dewi, and Rofiq (2020). It was concluded that disadvantaged students found it challenging to engage with their schoolwork and easier for these students lose motivation and eventually dropped out.

Apart from limited class interaction and uneven access to online resources, these assessments may feel "overwhelming or condemning to children" at a time when it is critical to provide opportunities for students to demonstrate what they know and where they are, as well as for teachers to adapt instruction to students' current development in order to advance their development and learning. Teachers in remote places lack the resources they have in their classrooms to analyze test results, compounding all of the challenges to meaningful and equitable monitoring and testing during the epidemic. In other words, in a classroom, teachers are better able to distinguish between a low score due to a student's lack of understanding of the material versus a low score due to the student's lack of understanding of the material versus a low score due to the student's frequent absences, emotional distress, or other factors. Meanwhile, Al-Awidi & Aldhafeeri (2017) has investigated factors that affect teachers' readiness to implement digital curriculum.

In recent studies by Moreno& Gortazar (2020); Hung (2015), including teacher attitudes, teacher training, and technical skills and commitment, learners' motivation was measured and their level of readiness to create and manage digital learning experiences for students was discussed, including teacher attitudes, teacher training, and technical skills and commitment. Hoffman (2020) has provided ways for increasing motivation for online work in his study.

Griffiths, Kerr, Stuart, Mistry, Klein, & Viner (2020) modelled Covasim, which describes individuals' contact networks stratified into household, school, workplace, and community layers, to avoid a second COVID-19 wave; while the working paper of UNESCO's (2020) mechanisms to avoid school closure, UNICEF (2020) provided clear and actionable guidance for safe operations through the prevention, early detection and control of COVID-19 in schools and other educational facilities.

Despite the fact that many schools are currently observing online training and looking for alternatives to address the issues of online and remote learning systems, many are beginning to adapt this new normal system and are currently missing face-to-face instruction. When the pandemic passes, it is assumed that pupils would return to school with lesser grades. It is perceived then that when the pandemic subsides, students will return to school with lower achievement. There are also concerns that the gap between high- and low-achieving students will become larger. Besides, the uncertainties on school's quality of education are at stake and share a common worry among teachers, learners and parents. Faculty and students' readiness to adopt it, its effectiveness and effect on learning remain uncharted.

CHEPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The study by Bozkurt et al. (2020) is one of the first to report on the impact of school disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in 31 nations. In addition to assessing each case individually, the study emphasized major themes that have emerged in these countries as a result of the interruption of education during COVID-19, such as (1) inequity and the digital divide, which have emerged in these countries as a result of the interruption of education during COVID-19, (2) the need for alternative assessment and evaluation methods and the needed switch to formative assessments through both synchronous and asynchronous means, and (3) the use of online proctoring services as a way to control for cheating and academic dishonesty.

As a result of a survey done on 303 university students and 56 educators in Norway, Hjelsvold et al. (2020) is one of the first studies to evaluate educators' feedback on remote learning during the COVID-19 lockout. According to the study, a lack of ready resources and a lack of time were significant impediments to a fast change to distance learning.

Concerning the COVID-19 Pandemic's Impact on Education: Challenges and Coping Strategies, Burgess & Sievertsen is a law firm founded by Burgess and Sievertsen (2020) Dawadi, Giri, and Simkhada (2020) assess the impact of the COVID-19 disruption on learning. Using online education, Bao (2020); During these unusual times, Ali (2020) captures the concept of constant learning. Peters, et al. (2020) described student experiences in the face of adversity.

Kvavadze (2020) studied the capacities of the country and its population, as well as Al-Samarrai, Samer's (2013) local education governance to continue the education process at the schools in the online form of distance learning; and Al-Samarrai, Infantes, & Gala (2020) concluded that the COVID-19 pandemic has dealt a heavy blow to an already-weak global economy with alarming speed; while Al-Samarrai, Infantes, &, & Lehe (2019) assessed how countries have mobilized additional resources for education and assesses their impact on access and learning outcomes.

Carlsson, Björn & Rooth (2020) estimate a causal effect of schooling on skills; Deblina, Saryodava Tripathy, Sujita, Kumarkar, Mivedita, Sharma (2020) assessed the knowledge, attitude, anxiety experience, and perceived mental healthcare during the COVID-19 pandemic; while Allen, Rowan & Singh (2018) discussed challenges and experiences of teachers and Msila (2015) challenges in teaching ICT in their classrooms.

In general, Fordjour, Koomson & Hanson (2020) study aimed at accessing the impact of Covid-19 on Ghana's teaching and learning; Sahu (2020) highlight the mental health of students and academic staff. The coping strategies were highlighted by Roddy, Amiet, Chung, Holt, Shaw, McKenzie, Garivaldis, Lodge & Mundy (2017) explored known best practice principles for online instructors, students, and student support and considers how these might apply to intensive online environments; Griffiths, Kerr, Stuart, Mistry, Klein & Viner (2020) modelled Covasim which describes individuals' contact networks stratified into household, school, workplace, and community layers, to avoid a second COVID-19 wave; while the working paper of UNESCO's (2020) mechanisms to avoid school closure; and UNICEF (2020) provided clear and actionable guidance for safe operations through the prevention, early detection and control of COVID-19 in schools and other educational facilities.

CHEPTER THREE RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

General objective: The study tried to describe student experiences and preferences in online and distance learning of the college students in public and private SUCs in Camarines Sur.

A. Specific Objectives: to Accomplish the General Objective, the Study

- Recorded and analyzed the experiences of students on online and distance learning;
- Identified the challenges they encountered;
- Determined their coping mechanism of students to deal with identified challenges;
- Described the initial support given by parents, and teachers to address these challenges; and
- Assessed the students' preferences on online and distance learning.

B. Research Methods

This study used the quantitative-qualitative research methods. The study described the student experiences and preferences in online and distance learning of the college students in Camarines Sur. Specifically, this study: (1) Recorded and analyzed the experiences of college students on online and distance learning; (2) Identified the challenges they encountered; (3) Determined their coping mechanism of students to deal with identified challenges; (4) Described the initial support given by parents, and teachers to address these challenges; and (5) Assessed the college preferences on online and distance learning.

The main respondents of the study were 1,225 college student learners of public and private SUCs in Camarines Sur using online learning system. This conduct of interview to respondents was done through an online survey. Different schools were distributed to cater different responses from the varied scenarios experienced by students in online and distance learning. Online interview was also conducted to clarify some responses and validate some data for interpretation.

CHAPTER FOUR RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Challenges of Students in Online and Distance Learning

This study focused on the Challenges faced by college students in online and distance learning. There were 1225 students who participated in the online survey from public and private state universities and colleges (SUCs) in Camarines Sur. Because of the pandemic, these challenges are necessary to assessto address some remedies in education. In the study of Elaish et al. (2019) & Garcia et al. (2018), they started to see schools, instructors, and students adopting e-learning tools that allow teachers to conduct interactive instruction, effortlessly exchange resources, and enhance student collaboration and involvement. Similar study of Barrot, Llenares, and Rosario (2021) discovered that the severity of obstacles and techniques differed from one student to the next. He concluded that multiple elements interacting. In this study the challenges that hinder them for attending classes, being late in online classes and their level of acquired knowledge and skills was sought.

➤ Attendance to Online and Distance Learning Classes

One of the challenges of students in online and distance learning to regularly attend their online classes. Attendance similar to face to face instructions are regularly checked by some teachers although others are considerate and others are strict. However, maintaining perfect attendance are struggles among college students.

- *S996: Complete attendance couldn't be obtained in this kind of mode of learning due tovarious reasons and hindrances I am experiencing amidst the pandemic.*

Based on the results of the study there are varied reasons why completing attendance among students. Most of them complained of poor internet connections while others experienced differently. Some responses were recorded and grouped according to theme to fully grasp the common causes of poor attendance to online classes. Table 1 shows the causes of poor attendance of student to online classes.

- *S126: It was difficult to perfect the attendance during online learning because there are unexpected factors that will affect your presence during virtual classes. One of the reasons why students were unattended during class hours is the internet connection. Personally, there was a time that I opt to mark myself absent during a meeting because my connectivity was poor that time. I thought that it'll not be a successful meeting for me because I can't understand the whole flow due to the fact that I'm experiencing some conflicts about my connection.*

Figure 1 shows the attendance of students in online and distance learning. The data shows that 280 or 22.9% of students ranked 8 as to their attendance to online classes; 228 or 18.6% ranked them 9; there are 185 or 15.1% ranke them 5, only 140 or 11.9% students out of 1,225 attend classes regularly. Meanwhile on 12 or 1% ranked 1 or 2 and 6 or 2.1% ranked them 3.

Fig 1. Challenges of Students Along Attendance in Classes.

Figure 1 shows that despite of the their struggle to online and distance learning dure to poor internet connections and other noted reasons, students are still struggling to In this study, the factors that affect the poor attendance of students are poor internet connections, Disappointments/Loss of Motivation, personal reasons, Teacher classroom management Lack of Teacher's Inputs, No load/Financial Problem, Household works/errands, Geographical Location/ weather condition, Unannounced blackouts/Power interruptions, and Poor mobile phones services.

- *Poor Internet Connectivity*

Based on the findings most of the students experienced Poor internet connection; lack of resources, no load/financial problems or support; doing household works/errands; the geographical Location/good weather condition since some of them are living in coastal areas; unannounced blackouts/power interruptions; health problem due to overexposure to laptops/mobile phones; lack of teacher motivation; lack of teacher's Inputs; disappointments/Loss of motivation; poor mobile phones services; disappointments; other personal reasons; and difficulty in learning using online and distance learning.

Internet connection is a major problem. No matter how much you tried to attend online classes, it will still be difficult especially for those, like us who live in secluded place. One time, I manage to open my data an hour before the sched of class but can't cope up with the lesson because of poor internet connectivity.

Table 1. Causes of Poor Attendance to Online Classes Due to Poor Internet Connectivity

Thematic Areas	Sample Responses
Poor internet connectiivity	Internet connection is a major problem. No matter how much you tried to attend online classes, it will still be difficult especially for those, like us who live in secluded place. One time, I manage to open my data an hour before the sched of class but can't cope up with the lesson because of poor internet connectivity.
	I can connect with virtual meetings appointed by my professors however there is always a disturbance concerning the unstable internet connection I have.
	It was convenient and easy to use, however, internet connection is the main problem that makes me incompetent.
	I've been to online class last first quarter. However, my experience wasn't that good because of the poor internet connection in our area. After the first quarter, I decided to switch into modular learning for I can access learning easier.
	First, I do not have a stable internet connection and that is already a big impact on my attendance during online classes. Second is I have things to be done and things to do that is far more important than completing my attendance every class, I sometimes attend the whole day but I seldom do it.

The data on students who regularly fail to attend online classes are also alarming. This indicate that there are students who are struggling and left behind due to internet connection which led to their disappointment to attend regular classes.

• *Disappointment/Loss of Motivation*

Because of the different struggles students may have encountered, one of the hindrances that caused them to miss classes are disappointment to challenging situation which led to their loss of motivation to continue schooling.

Table 2. Causes of Poor Attendance to Online Classes Due to Disappointment/Loss of Motivation

Disappointments/Loss of Motivation	Tiring Boring Hard Worst I always had a hard time studying in this type of educational system. So hustle and depressing, it is because sometimes the teacher didn't understand our part of being student. we all know that some student can't afford the gadgets and also the internet on that will be used in online classes
	I rate it 6 because..as based on my experiences not all the time we are able to access the stable internet connection, and there is always a sudden brownout without notice, another is that sometimes we couldn't afford to buy load, also some instructor did not consider it as a valid reason, cause as we start the online
	Class it is a very common excuse but it is the truth, so it is the reason why me and lot of student couldn't make to attend online class
	There are a lot of technical errors that happens and also sometimes we do not meet our expectation during discussion.
	In this situation studies is not the only Our priority we have also a commitment in our home, we have alot of task in our homethat's why sometimes studying is not our priorities and sometimes it just end it up on neglected

Some students also replied that online classes are tiring, boring, hard and worst. This is rooted and magnified from their difficulty to connect with stable internet. Their disappointment with this new educational system is also alarming among students because of some other stressors like lack of finances, power interruption and even inconsiderate teacher.

- *I always had a hard time studying in this type of educational system.*
- *So hustle and depressing, it is because sometimes the teacher didn't understand our part of being student. We all know that some student can't afford the gadgets and also the internet on that will be used in online classes*
- *I rate it 6 because as based on my experiences not all the time we are able to access the stable internet connection, and there is always a sudden brownout without notice, another is that sometimes we couldn't afford to buy load, also some instructor did not consider it as a valid reason, cause as we start the online class it is a very common excuse but it is the truth, so it is the reason why me and lot of student couldn't make to attend online class*

➤ *Teachers' Factor*

This is also an alarming findings that one of the causes of the challenges of students to attend classes is due to teachers' inefficiency, poor classroom management and lack of inputs while requiring students to comply numerous modules without consideration on deadline, for some. Although, generally teachers are lenient to consider the scenarios, some students complains, as reflected on the following responses as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Causes of Poor Attendance to Online Classes Due to Teacher's Factor

Teacher classroom management	Being forced by a professor to show up during classes During my first semester months attendance is a must for the instructors. With my experience not all students are capable having an online class but for my side I am
	always attending when we have our online class. Some of our instructor are considerate but some are strict when it comes to attending with their zoom or Google meet classes.
Lack of Teacher's Inputs	for me as a student I'm also satisfied for online class but there's a time that I'm experiencing difficulty's such as answering math problem because our instructor sometimes didn't online of that time so that we need to do is to search through google for additional information to solve it. But I wish that this pandemic will end to have a face to face classes to better understand the subject matter. sometimes i'm not attending online class because of two reason. First no data or no financial support for my expenses in load second poor connectivity or signal sometimes i cannot understand the instructor discussion so i just close my data para dai sayang ang load ko. Some faculty members rarely attend their respective class, that is why few students, including me lost interest in their subject class.
	R10: It's hard to study when the internet is too slow so sometimes student like me can't attend but but I review the modules so I can keep up, some teachers not attending they just post the module and activity in the Google classroom so sometimes we didn't understand the lesson.
	Lack of learning to be gain
	As what I told before ,we had a schedule but then, sometimes the instructor gonna be late to update us about the attendance so I rate as 5 because once the time start at the given subject then the instructor is not updating us ,we do our daily routine that cause of being late when we forgot to check again the gc if the teachers active .
	I rarely attend our class on time. I usually join in the meeting five minutes after the link is sent.

These responses was further highlighted by the response of saying:

- *There are a lot of technical errors that happens and also sometimes we do not meet our expectation during discussion.*

Some of the students complains of lack of teacher's input and motivation, some responses noted, are as follows:

- *For me as a student I'm also satisfied for online class but there's a time that I'm experiencing difficulty's such as answering math problem because our instructor sometimes didn't online of that time so that we need to do is to search through google for additional information to solve it. But I wish that this pandemic will end to have a face to face classes to better understand the subject matter.*

This sample response indicates that there are students who got disappointed to attend classes because of lack of teacher's input. This indicate that although students are starting to learn at their own pace independently, the input of teachers is also significant. The presence of online library and online sources like Google and other platforms are not enough. The guidance and inputs of teachers are still demanded especially on difficult subjects such as Mathematics.

- *It's hard to study when the internet is too slow so sometimes student like me can't attend but but I review the modules so I can keep up, some teachers not attending they just post the module and activity in the Google classroom so sometimes we didn't understand the lesson.*

Some of the difficulty of students to learn concepts is shown in this sample response:

- *I was excited about distance learning because there will be less socialization required, but truthfully, online classes have depleted me; I don't comprehend the lessons and I only do my activities to meet the deadline.*

This response indicate that although teachers may opt to modular learning, they may also conduct initial instructions on the learning materials they share to students. This imply that teachers may further add their burden if teachers input and presence are missing.

- *sometimes i'm not attending online class because of two reason. First no data or no finacial support for my expenses in load second poor connectivity or signal sometimes i cannot understand the instructor discussion so i just close my data para dai sayang angload ko (I just close my phone data so that it will not be wasted).*
- *Some faculty members rarely attend their respective class, that is why few students, including me lost interest in their subject class.*

➤ *Lack of Learning to be Gain*

These responses indicate that regular attendance to online and distance learning are also expected by students among teachers. This also include their punctuality. Some teachers comelate so that some students also logged in late due to limited data or load. This indicate that some students consume data because of teachers coming late at class.

- *As what I told before ,we had a schedule but then ,sometimes the instructor gonna be late to update us about the attendance so I rate as 5 because once the time start at the given subject then the instructor is not updating us ,we do our daily routine that cause ofbeing late when we forgot to check again the gc if the teachers active .*
- *I rarely attend our class on time. I usually join in the meeting five minutes after the link issent.*
- *Sometimes I'm joining our virtual meetings in the middle of discussion because I don'thave sometimes an mobile data and also I have somethings doing at home.*
- *As a student of online class learning for me is difficult. Because so much more strugglesand problems that I've encountered, Not for mental health but also in physical and financial.*

Table 4. Causes of Poor Attendance to Online Classes Due to Difficulty in Learning

Difficulty in Learning	It was a lot harder to understand some lessons in thisonline and distance learning. It hard to adapt, but I can make some adjustments
	Difficulties in terms of passing our modules
	I was excited about distance learning because there will be less socialization required, but truthfully, online classeshave depleted me; I don't comprehend the lessons and I only do my activities to meet the deadline.

Teachers may also influence the students’ motivation to attend classes if teachers consider attendance strictly or considerately if there are valid reasons. This indicate that teachers may display different classroom management but teachers’ attendance are felt among students during this tryingtimes.

- *Being forced by a professor to show up during classes.*
- *During my first semester months attendance is a must for the instructors. With my experience not all students are capable having an online class but for my side I am always attending when we have our online class. Some of our instructor are consideratebut some are strict when it comes to attending with their zoom or Google meet classes.*

Table 5. Causes of Poor Attendance to Online Classes Due to Other Causes

No load/Financial Problems	As a student of online class learning for me is difficult. Because so much more struggles and problems that I've encountered, Not for mental health but also in physical andfinancial. Face to face classes is much better than online class. Sometimes I'm joining our virtual meetings in the middle ofdiscussion because I don't have sometimes an mobile data and also I have some things doing at home.
Household works/errands	R21: I have several household works to fulfill, and that iswhy I cannot attend online discussions regularly. I only rate 6 since I often attend classes due to errands thati needed to do and we do not have stable internet. I always attend synchronous meeting but sometimes I can'tattend because of house works.
Geographical Location/weather condition	I experienced that online class is not easy, especially to those people who are in the coastal area who has poor internet connection. And it has many disadvantages to us like attending class on time, participating in oral recitation,submitting activity on time, and soon. Then sometimes some professor send activity even though their class hour isnot their time to teach and also they send late activities at midnight. When the weather is fine then I am able to attend
Unannounced blackouts/Power interruptions	There are a lot of barrier in order to attend the class fully oron time one of which is the problem in internet connection,unannounced black out, and more. There is also one time that I am not able to attend the whole class because suddenly the internet connection was lost and I am in the midst of reciting at that time.
Poor mobile phones services	I can't attend due to the weakness of the internet, sometimes the line is cut and my cellphone goes off every time we have a Gmeet. It's hard, I try to attend every Gmeet, but it also leaves on purpose, I don't know what theproblem is.

Among other reasons students may be considered are as follows:

➤ *Geographical Location*

I experienced that online class is not easy, especially to those people who are in the costal area who has poor internet connection. And it has many disadvantages to us like attending class on time, participating in oral recitation, submitting activity on time, and soon. Then sometimes some professor send activity even though their class hour is not their time to teach and also theysend late activities at midnight.

➤ *Weather Condition*

- *When the weather is fine then I am able to attendIf the weather is fine.*
- *I hop from one island to another just to get signal.Unannounced blackouts/Power interruptions*
- *There are a lot of barrier in order to attend the class fully or on time one of which is the problem in internet connection, unannounced black out, and more. There is also one time that I am not able to attend the whole class because suddenly the internet connection was lost and I am in themidst of reciting at that time.*
- *Health problem*
- *Absence because of health problem*
- *Overexposure to cellphone, I feel dizzy and having a headaches always.*

➤ *Personal reasons*

- *I'm not attending class if I have an emergency at home. Nagbabantay ako ng tindahan ,that's why I'm not active in class.*
- *Now there is a pandemics and online class is more difficult for me because I combine work withmy studies, so sometimes I miss class time. One reason my attendance lowered my grade, especially since I didn't have a cell phone available, and worse was due to lack of time my attendance also dropped some of my subjects.*

Due to personal reasons I cannot join the class

Some of the students also complain of their household obligations which hinder them to attend classes regularly with concentration:

- *R21: I have several household works to fulfill, and that is why I cannot attend online discussionsregularly.*
- *I only rate 6 since i often attend classes due to errands that i needed to do and we do not havestable internet.*
- *I always attend synchronous meeting but sometimes I can't attend because of houseworks.*

Studies proved that in developing counties, even when students are able to attend school, many must do additional market or domestic work when they are not at school (Reich, 2014). These responsibilities away from school are shown to seriously impact school attendance. Using the UNICEF’s Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS) from 2000, Edmonds (2007) assessed school attendance ratesand found that they declined with hours of work in instances when children worked more than eight hours a week. Students who spent more hours on work outside of the household had a much greater decline in school attendance compared to those who worked within the household, but whether the work was categorized as being market or domestic work was inconsequential for school attendance.

➤ *Punctuality*

Another challenge in online and distance classes is the punctuality of students. Due to some factors and reasons, some students find it hard to come on class on time. Chart 2 shows the data.

Fig 2 Punctuality of Student in Online and Distance Learning

The data shows that only 138 or 11.3% out of 1, 225 respondents got on time during online classes; 256 or 20.9 % rated it 9 while 303 or 24.7% rated it 8 with highest responses. Meanwhile only 15 or 1 percent, 8 or 0.7% and 24 or 2% fail to attend classes on time. This indicates that despite of poor internet connections and other challenges, students made sure to attend classes on time.

Table 6. Challenges on the Punctuality of Students Along Lack of Discipline/Focus

Thematic Areas	Sample Responses
Lack of discipline/focus	S2: I always wake up late
	Sometimes, I cannot attend the class on time because of online games, I woke up late, and not aware of my schedules.
	Though I'm always present in our online classes, there are times that I'm late, it is because of the internet connection and also sometimes I wake up in the morning so late.
	I rarely attend our class on time. I usually join in the meeting five minutes after the link is sent.
	Having a hard time reconnecting on our internet session
	for the time of the online class, I can't say that I can't enter at the right time because of the lack or very weak connection, sometimes I can still enter online but it also doesn't take long because the connection is down, especially when there is only data and there is not enough money for the load

- *Lack of discipline/focus*

Based on the findings, students lack discipline to attend their class on time. Some of them woke up late so that they missed their classes especially in the morning. Some studies show that when students come to class late, it can disrupt the flow of a lecture or discussion, distract other students, impede learning, and generally erode class morale. Moreover, if left unchecked, lateness can become chronic and spread throughout the class.

- *S2: I always wake up late*

The presence of online games also affect their focus to attend online classes and attend early on class the next morning. For most people, on-line gaming is one of the best past time that they acquire specially for teenagers, youngsters and students. According to Kuss & Griffiths (2012), during school hours, students tend to feel stressed due to loads of school works and through playing it will relive their stress. Meanwhile, Rock said, all these technologies are very good at distracting people.

- *Sometimes, I cannot attend the class on time because of online games, I woke up late, and not aware of my schedules.*

Some students may also be aware of the importance of punctually but intently logged in few minutes after to make sure the teacher is already around or assure that their load are purposely spent. In this case, student rarely attend class on time as she waits for the teacher to send its link. It indicates that students value their resources spent rather than joining online class on time. Students don't perceive the beginning of class as important. It implies that the first minutes of class are often the most critical, since this is when instructors share important administrative information, present the day's agenda, frame the content of the lecture or discussion, connect the current content to past content, and so forth. Yet students may not recognize this.

- *I rarely attend our class on time. I usually join in the meeting five minutes after the link is sent.*

It implies that students don't take responsibility for themselves. While the majority of students are responsible and mature, there are some who struggle with the independence college provides and who fail to do what they need to do (e.g., set an alarm clock, allow sufficient time to get ready in the morning, figure out the bus schedule) to get to class on time. They may also not recognize that it is their responsibility to communicate with instructors when they are unable to meet their obligations (e.g., because of physical or emotional problems or conflicting obligations). Students of the millennial generation, who are used to a high degree of parental involvement and oversight in their lives and schedules, may have particular difficulty adjusting to these responsibilities.

- *Household chores and errands*

The relationship between education and socioeconomic status has been demonstrated in studies of the developed and the developing world. Along with the effect on a child's presence in school and the quality of that schooling, work and chores also impact academic achievement (Reich, et al 2020).

- *S4: Sometime I can't attend class because my father ordered me to go to market to buy a dish to cook in lunch so while I was going to town I was listening to the class. but sometimes I can't attend because of what I'm asked to do at home.*

- *How they can stay punctual in online classes if they are given responsibilities at home. They are tasked to do chores or help their parents make money, making it impossible for them to attend their online classes. With this, the rate of student attendance slows down.*

- *Well I don't always arrive on time (Google Meet/Zoom Meeting) due to some household chores that I still need to finish before fixing myself and attend the online class.*

Table 7. Challenges on the Punctuality of Students Due Household Chores and Errands

Household chores and errands	S4: Sometime I cant attend class because my father ordered me to go to market to buy a dish to cook in lunch so while I was going to town I was listening to theclass. but sometimes I can't attend because of what I'm asked to do at home.
	How they can stay punctual in online classes if they are given responsibilities at home. They are tasked to do chores or help their parents make money, making it impossible for them to attend their online classes. With this, the rate of student attendance slows down.
	Well I don't always arrive on time (Google Meet/Zoom Meeting) due to some household chores that I still need to finish before fixing myself and attend the online class

As indicated in the responses of students, many of them are obliged to do domestic/household chores while attending or before attending school which made them late. Poverty also among low income families is also undeniable to earn some living while schooling. It shows that while in home education, some considers household obligation a priority over their online classes and school requirements done on time.

• *Lack of communication*

This response indicate that poor or lack of communication between teachers and students affect punctuality of students. This implies that information and punctuality rules are not properly disseminated. Although some teachers assigned a class beadle or information officer, constant communication is required to let students feel of their punctuality issues. It implies that teachers should set deadlines for tasks and requirements may also be reached to all students, fully understood and cleared among them.

• *Poor information dissemination*

Students in the Philippines confronted several interrelated barriers as they tried to adapt to online learning. Most frequently encountered were difficulty adjusting learning styles, having to perform responsibilities at home, and poor communication between educators and learners (Baticulon, R.E., Sy, J.J., Alberto, N.R.I. *et al.*, 2021). It implies that there is a need to inculcate to students that it is their responsibility to communicate with teachers if they are experiencing a legitimate problem that will cause them to be late or otherwise miss class time.

• *Geographical Location*

Based on initial interviews, some of the student-respondents are living in coastal areas where internet connectivity is very challenging. They have to hop from one island to another, climb a tree or stay at the mountain peak just to get signal. This implies that there are students who are struggling forthis mode of learning.

• *It takes minutes to find an area where the internet is at least stable for the Google meet*

Table 8. Challenges on the Punctuality of Students Due to Poor Internet Connectivity

Poor internet connectivity	Sometimes I'm early but I'm mostly I'm almost 15-20 minutes late depending on the signal.
	It's really hard to maintain the value of punctuality because I'm always facing difficultyin attending online discussion due to poor internet connectivity.
	Due to unavailability of internet access, responsibilities at home, and other personal reason, I wasn't able to join online meetings.
	My punctuality in class will depend on internetconnection. If the internet is poor, I came late and sometimes I didn't attend.
	Sometimes, the connections hinder us to be early. And other responsibility

• *Poor internet connection*

Another major problem in online and distance learning is poor internet connectivity. May studentsstruggle to avail of quality internet providers. In the Philippines, there are around 7 internet providers however, these providers are receiving negative feedback due to intermittent or slow connections.

Ongoing construction of line services also delayed or cause absence of internet service for a time.

- *My punctuality in class will depend on internet connection. If the internet is poor, I came late andsometimes I didn't attend.*
- *It's really hard to maintain the value of punctuality because I'm always facing difficulty inattending online discussion due to poor internet connectivity.*
- *Sometimes I'm early but I'm mostly I'm almost 15-20 minutes late depending on the signal.*
- *Due to unavailability of internet access, responsibilities at home, and other personal reason, I wasn't able to join online meetings.*
- *Sometimes, the connections hinder us to be early.*

- *Though I'm always present in our online classes, there are times that I'm late, it is because of the internet connection and also sometimes I wake up in the morning so late.*
- *Having a hard time reconnecting on our internet session*
- *For the time of the online class, I can't say that I can't enter at the right time because of the lack or very weak connection, sometimes I can still enter online but it also doesn't take long because the connection is down, especially when there is only data and there is not enough money for the load*

As of the moment, our country's average internet speed ranges from 3 to 7 Mbps, which is hardly enough to load a 30-second Instagram video, let alone a three hour long lecture. Students and educators alike are suffering from the sudden shift to online learning, and the added toll of an unreliable internet connection is something that has posed a challenge to most academic institutions (Honasan, 2021).

Table 9. Challenges on the Punctuality of Students Due to Difficulty in Completion of Tasks/Modules

Difficulty in Completion of tasks/modules	Honestly, I or we are no longer care about punctuality as long as we submitted all the requirements, quizzes and others matter.
	Being on time when passing modules was fine forme at the start of the school year, but now it just stresses me out, and I find it difficult to encourage myself to do my assignments.
	Sometimes late because of having a hard time submitting the requirements

• *Difficulty in Completion of tasks/modules*

Modules are increasingly being used in many countries as a way of organising an online curriculum due to the pandemic. As a consequence, many course books are now structured on the basis of “modules” rather than “units”. Teachers are required to prepare a unit of work in a course of instruction that is virtually self-contained and a method of teaching that is based on the concept of building up skills and knowledge in discrete. A module is a set of learning opportunities organized around a well - defined topic which contains the elements of ordinate dictation, categorical objectives, edifying cognition activities, and evaluation utilizing criterion - referenced measures UNESCO (1988).

The following responses indicate difficulty in completion of tasks and modules over being punctual in online classes. Some students rather submit all requirements and assessment as part of their compliance. For others, completion is easier at first but gradually losses their motivation when given additional tasks on deadline. Some also find hard time submitting due to poor internet connections and lack of teachers input.

- *Honestly, I or we are no longer care about punctuality as long as we submitted all therequirements, quizzes and others matter.*
- *Being on time when passing modules was fine for me at the start of the school year, but now itjust stresses me out, and I find it difficult to encourage myself to do my assignments.*
- *Sometimes late because of having a hard time submitting the requirements*

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED), put together distance learning options that include online platforms, offline modules, or a combination of the two, called blended or flexible learning. But distance learning has made inequities, especially around the digital divide, more apparent than ever before (Santos, 2020).

Many students, too, still need the internet to do supplemental research on more complex assignments. The 6.5 million students who have access to the internet, approximately 20 percent use computer shops or other public places to go online. Worse, 2.8 million students have no way of going online at all. This is especially common in the rural areas where 53 percent of the population live and where both internet access and speed can be a challenge. Despite the effort that goes into printing materials, K-12 teachers are still expected to be available for consultations either online (usually through Facebook Messenger) or by text. The response below demonstrates how Module completions are done at ease:

- *In terms of completion of modules, it is not hard to comply. As a Flexi-kit student, deadline is nota problem for me because our due date of all activities is every end of clusters. I mean, we all know that we have 2 semester in one year. But in our school, 1 semester is divided into 2. So meaning, if we have 2 semester in one year, we have 4 clusters in one year. In one semester, we have 2 clusters. Cluster 1 and cluster 2. So, in every cluster, we have 4 subjects. So it is not hassle for us to comply an activities.*

• *Forgetfulness/Poor time management*

Due to poor time management and other domestic responsibilities, students tend to forget their class schedules. Some student also do some extra job to help their family earn a living, which caused them hardship to manage their class schedules.

- *Poor time management is one the reasons why sometimes I attend to class late. There are times that I am late because of some other things or matters to do.*

- *Because to be honest everytime I participated in online class, sometimes I'm not prepared, and conflict regarding in balancing the time between other stuffs and classes.*
- *As I began college, being punctual became one of my traits, but when it became online and distance learning I sometimes forgot that I had a class due to family responsibilities (doing household chores) and working as a sari sari storekeeper, and sometimes the inability to join the class on time due to internet problem.*

The primary achievement of distance and regular students is managing time effectively.

Mismanagement disturbs the academic achievements of learners. Time administration plays a significant role in improving learners' performance and accomplishments. It is a skill to manage time and every learner must familiar and command on this skill for the sake of better results. (Ahmad, Batool, Hussain, 2019). It implies that students don't recognize how their lateness affects others. Students may fail to realize the level of disruption that coming in late creates for their fellow classmates and for teachers.

• *Lack of Resources/Gadget*

Among the 1, 225 respondents, 91% owned a smartphone and 9% had a laptop or desktop computer. To access online resources, 89% had a postpaid internet subscription while 11% used prepaid mobile data. Under prevailing conditions, only nearly half students (41%) considered themselves physically and mentally capable of engaging in online learning. Some of their responses are as follows:

- *Nakikihiram lang po ako ng cellphone. Minsan di ko magamit kasi kay Nanay yun. Dun po tumatawag an kapatid ko nasa Manila. (I just borrow a mobile phone to my Mother who owns it. We use the same whenever my sister from Manila called up)*
- *During class time or online class, the situation is difficult because when there is a sudden Gmeet case and there is no load, you will not be able to attend immediately. It's even harder because my phone's storage is no longer available so I have to delete my other apps including Gmeet*
- *Not all of the time I stick to the preferred start time of the class due to signal also and load problem*

Table 10. Challenges on the Punctuality of Students Due to Forgetfulness/Poor Time Management

Forgetfulness/Poor time management	Poor time management is one the reasons why sometimes I attend to class late.
	There are times that I am late because of some other things or matters to do.
	because to be honest everytime I participated in online class, sometimes I'm not prepared, and conflict regarding in balancing the time between other stuffs and classes.
	As I began college, being punctual became one of my traits, but when it became online and distance learning I sometimes forgot that I had a class due to family responsibilities (doing household chores) and working as a sari sari storekeeper, and sometimes the inability to join the class on time due to internet problem.
Lack of resources	During class time or online class, the situation is difficult because when there is a sudden Gmeet case and there is no load, you will not be able to attend immediately. It's even harder because my phone's storage is no longer available so I have to delete my other apps including Gmeet
	Not all of the time I stick to the preferred start time of the class due to signal also and load problem
Negative Attitudes towards online classes	in this situation studies is not the only Our priority we have also a commitment in our home, we have alot of task in our home that's why sometimes studying is not our priorities and sometimes it just end it up on neglected

Due to poverty, some students cannot attend classes regularly and on time. Some Parents cannot avail to provide regular load for every day classes. Some interviews conducted revealed that they are finding finances for their billings, foods and other household needs, while loading and providing android for some seems difficult and impractical.

• *Negative Attitudes towards online classes*

Another barrier in embracing the new normal is the negative attitudes of students towards online and distance learning. Students tend to compare traditional or face-to-face instructions to online-distance learning. For many students, the physical presence of teachers in the classroom have impact to learners' performance and progress rather than online ones.

- *I don't like online classes. I prefer face-to-face classes. I learn better than online.*
- *Unlike in face to face, in this situation studies is not the only priority we have also a commitment in our home, we have alot of task in our home that's why sometimes studying is not our priorities and sometimes it just end it up neglected*
- *I learn a little in online. I miss face to face!*

It also implies that students are experiencing emotional or psychological problems.

Several psychological and emotional conditions can undermine students’ motivation to get to class on time. Indeed, a hallmark symptom of conditions such as depression includes a decreased motivation to engage in normal daily activities. In addition, prescription medications can interfere with motivation and may disrupt sleep patterns, which may indirectly affect students’ ability to get to class in a timely manner.

• *Difficulty in Learning*

The response below reveals that students find difficulty in adjusting to online and distance learning. Although this method has started last upon the onslaught of the COVID-19 pandemic, still there are students who are struggling and eventually feel frustrated and loss their motivation.

Table 11. Challenges on the Punctuality of Students Due to Difficulty in Learning

Difficulty in Learning	There are times that I attended to the class really late. I remember the time when I attended one of my major subjects in the afternoon where are our teacher was already wrapping up the whole discussion for that period. I felt so embarrassed. That time, I feel like I am not belong to the class since I already missed the whole discussion, I really didn't understand what our teacher is talking about. The whole class was participating and I am just there, listening to them and little by little absorbing the whole lessons that have been discussed. Which only made me frustrated because I really did not get to understand the lesson that caused me to just left the online class and waited for the learning material that was posted on our VLP (Virtual Learning Portal)
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• *Teacher Factor*

The observance of online and distance does not end the very role of teachers to become available to all students need. If students usually got late, this implies that students’ expectations are out of line with the instructor’s. There is wide variation in the classroom styles of instructors. Some instructors are bothered if students arrive a few minutes late; others are not. There is also a wide variation in departmental cultures, some of which may tolerate lateness more than others. International students, moreover, may come from cultures with a less strict emphasis on timeliness. Because of this variability, students’ expectations regarding being on time may be substantially different from those of a particular instructor. Moreover, students may have an incorrect set of expectations regarding lateness in certain kinds of courses, such as courses that meet in the evening, are large, meet for 3 to 4 hours or more, or have relatively informal formats (e.g., studios, labs).

- *Students are not punctual, and the same goes with some of the instructors. In fact there is a point that I almost could not attend my class because my instructor could not meet us in his/her allotted time. I only have two subjects at that time and both already passes its time so assuming that my classes end during that time I turned off my data. Luckily, I later on again decided to open it and saw immediately that pops up in my messenger account.*
- *Satisfied. There are times when the internet connection becomes slow but it never affect my attendance in class. I am often, minutes late to the class but it only happens when I missed the time for the class or when our instructor suddenly sent the online class' link earlier than our scheduled time.*
- *As what I told before, we had a schedule but then, sometimes the instructor gonna be late to update us about the attendance so I rate as 5 because once the time start at the given subject then the instructor is not updating us ,we do our daily routine that cause of being late when we forgot to check again the gc if the teachers active.*
- *Most of the professors are adjusting their time on our synchronous without us knowing so we ended up being late.*

The above response imply that teachers shall Model desired behavior. Teachers should sent link before class scheduled hours, arrive and get the class started on time. Dismiss the class on time, too.

Students are more likely to respect time if teachers respect theirs.

- *We have a teacher that even if we attend her class in Gmeet. Sometimes she marked us an absent because her reason our name did not pop up on her record which is very unfair. I prioritize her subject, but now it already fixed because we take screenshots on every meetings and attach it on attendance in google classroom. But we do not retrieve the time that we are present and marked as absent.*

This implies that teachers should be careful in giving attendance or punctuality remarks on students who are honestly present. It indicates that technology shall not replace regular checking of attendance since teachers still have the prerogative to impose classroom management with equity and fairness.

- *When it comes to passing of outputs I'm on time. The only problem that I have encountered in this state is that some instructors wants their papers to be submitted according to their own time without consulting some students if they can make it.*
- *I remember one of my instructor gave us 4 or 5 activity today and we need to submit it next week the pressure and stress we felt today how can we get inspiration to answer if they giving as a speedily answer that is the reason why most of the student now they don't learn anything rather they just submit the activity for requirement of the school.*

Table 12. Challenges on the Punctuality of Students Due to Teacher Factor

Teacher Factor	Students are not punctual, and the same goes with some of the instructors. In fact there is a point that I almost could not attend my class because my instructor could not meet us in his/her allotted time. I only have two subjects at that time and both already passes its time so assuming that my classes end during that time I turned off my data. Luckily, I later on again decided to open it and saw immediately that pops up in my messenger account.
	Satisfied. There are times when the internet connection becomes slow but it never affect my attendance in class. I am often, minutes late to the class but it only happens when I missed the time for the class or when our
	Instructor suddenly sent the online class' link earlier than our scheduled time.
	When it comes to passing of outputs I'm on time. The only problem that I have encountered in this state is that some instructors wants their papersto be submitted according to their own time without consulting some students if they can make it.
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	As what I told before, we had a schedule but then ,sometimes the instructor gonna be late to update us about the attendance so I rate as 5because once the time start at the given subject then the instructor is notupdating us ,we do our daily routine that cause of being late when we forgot to check again the gc if the teachers active .
	I remember one of my instructors gave us 4 or 5 activity for a day and we need to submit it next week the pressure and stress we felt today how can we get inspiration to answer if they giving as a speedily answer that is the reason why most of the student now they don't learn anything rather they just submit the activity for requirement of the school
	Most of the professors are adjusting their time on our synchronous without us knowing so we ended up being late.
	My punctuality on submission of requirements and being on time in attendance depends on the strength of network connectivity. Like for example, there are some instructors who gave us three hours to consumein answering modules and submission of requirements, sometimes the network connection specifically when there is bad weather, it becomes a hindrance to be punctual on submission of requirements.
	8, kasi pumapasok naman sa tamang oras yung mga prof kaso nga lang masyadong mabagal yung discussion kasi minsan na iinterrupt lang talagayung discussion dahil sa poor internet connection and kailangan pang mag hintay ng nga ilang minutes bago makacontinue sa klase.

- *My punctuality on submission of requirements and being on time in attendance depends on the strength of network connectivity. Like for example, there are some instructors who gave us three hours to consume in answering modules and submission of requirements, sometimes the network connection specifically when there is bad weather, it becomes a hindrance to be punctual on submission of requirements.*

This implies that students need teachers to be flexible especially we are under pandemic. Some considerations may be extended to students with valid reasons. Online and distance learning is considered challenging to most students, thus flexible learning can also be applied. It also implies that students must be aware that there is no consequence to being late. The consequences associated with a behavior help determine whether or not that behavior will be repeated. If the consequences are negative, the behavior is less likely to reoccur. This applies to coming late to class. If instructors fail to respond to or penalize lateness, or do so inconsistently, the behavior is likely to continue.

- *8, kasi pumapasok naman sa tamang oras yung mga prof kaso nga lang masyadong mabagal yung discussion kasi minsan na iinterrupt lang talaga yung discussion dahil sa poor internet connection and kailangan pang mag hintay ng nga ilang minutes bago makacontinue sa klase.*
- *(8, because the professors also attend class early but sometimes their discussions were too slow, since it is interrupted by poor internet connectios and you have to wait for some minutes before we continue our classes)*

This response reveal that teachers also encounter some connectivity issues due to poor internet connection. The digital gap and internet problems continue to keep students from learning and teachers from teaching. Teachers, too, face connectivity challenges as a result of a poor internet connection, according to this response. Students and teachers are still unable to learn due to the digital divide and internet issues. For many students and their families, as well as teachers, the digital divide is very real.

This refers to the fact that many kids, families, and teachers do not have access to computers for a period of time. The educational experience of the students without the critical technology both becomes unfair and unequal (Vereen, 2020).

➤ *Level of Acquired Knowledge or Skill*

Rapid advances in information and communications technology in the digital age have brought about significant changes in the practice of distance education (DE) worldwide. DE practitioners in the Philippines' open university have coined the term 'open and distance e-learning' (ODEL) to refer to the new forms of DE, which are characterized by the convergence of an open learning

philosophy, DE pedagogies, and e-learning technologies (Arinto, 2016). However, despite of the many studies on the advantages of online and distance learning, students are still facing a lot of challenges. The following responses, saying the disadvantages of online and distance learning using modules.

- *Some of our subjects especially our major subjects I can't get it because its hard for me to understand especially on our fingerprint because there is no one who will guide and teachus how this subject works on our course.*

The above response imply that there is a need for practical and laboratory activities for boardcourses. Although teachers have provided students with recorded learning videos and module and other printed materials, teachers have to meet their students in some instances where face to face instruction is required.

- *Honestly, i am not learning at all. I couldn't barely understand some of the lessons and the fact that my course is in line in the medical field, I am struggling to understand suchterminologies and discussion.*

This response imply that students need to be redirected on the possible resources for hard to define terminologies. Para medical courses belong to courses which include numerous terminologies that need to be defined conceptually and operationally as they are to be used in their future career.

- *I find it difficult to gain knowledge especially when a teacher only gives modules but rarely communicates with us. Self-learning is not the best way of learning, I do exert effort in the idea, however, it's just hard to grasp learning in this kind of modality.*

This imply that the good academic performance of student although they are required for independent learning is also required. The inputs of teachers are still wanting.

Fig 3 Challenges Encountered by Students Along the Level of Acquired Knowledge and Skills.

Chart 3 shows that that their level of acquired skills is only 7.3%, or 89 out of 1,225 respondents felt satisfied with online and distance learning with a rank of 10 as a highest; this is followed by 250 or 20.4% of students while 382 or 31.2 % of students rated 8 as to the their level of required knowledge and skills. Meanwhile, 12 or 1 % rated it lowest followed by 7 responses or (0.6%), 17 or 1.4% of level of satisfaction. Table 4 shows the table of responses.

- *Difficulty in Learning*

The following responses signify students' difficulty in learning. For most students online and distance learning is considered challenging because of limited teacher and student interactions, limited class discussion, and students' burden for self-study since there is limited inputs from teachers, too.

- *As for I'm an IT student, self-study isn't enough, I find a hard time comprehending the modules/codes. Face to face is really needed.*
- *Konti lang yung natutunan kasi sa online class parang self study lang. (I only learn a little in this online classes since self-study)*

Table 13. Challenges of Students on Level of Acquired Knowledge and Skills Along Difficulty in Learning

Thematic Areas	Sample Responses
Difficulty in Learning	As for I am, self-study isn't enough, I find a hard time comprehending the modules/codes. Face to face is really needed
	Only a portion of the discussed lessons can be absorbed by your mind. You need to study smarter.
	Konti lang yung natutunan kasi sa online class parang self-study lang I can say it's above average, because sometimes I can catch up with my lessons easily. But having troubles for understanding is normal for a student
Negative Attitudes towards online and distance learning	Face to face classes is better than this so called online class. University and schools are very good environment than our house. Our home can be distracted sometimes. The level of acquired knowledge that I get is good but not quite. Relying solely on online education may hinder the holistic development of students and many may underperform later in their professional and personal life
	May natutunan naman kaso supper unti unlike sa f2f, kasi ngayong inline class nakakatamad talaga mag aral, ni hindi na nga ako ang rereview kasi open notes naman ang pweden naman mag search, tsaka ss dami ng gagawin sa bahay plus sa klase mas uunahin talaga yung sa bahay kasinsa school kaya naman i search yung mga sagot, kaya bat mo pa papahirapan sarili mo, and yun na nga gaya ng sinabiko kanina internet connection and yun focus ng mga student yan din ang reason kaya unti lang natutunan.
	I gave it a 4 because I think this online learning is not effective. Still learning lesson though is not the same and as better in face to face learning.

The above responses indicate that technology students need practical applications. Although all materials are readily available in the internet the feeling of assurance of learning is necessary among students.

- *Only a portion of the discussed lessons can be absorbed by your mind. You need to study smarter.*
- *I can say it's above average, because sometimes I can catch up with my lessons easily. But having troubles for understanding is normal for a student.*

The last two responses imply that students possess different types and level of intelligences. For some students independent or self-study may be easier but may not be convenient to regular or disadvantaged students. There are also cases wherein students are not technologically-gifted.

Table 14. Challenges of Students on Level of Acquired Knowledge and Skills Along Poor Assessment

Poor Assessment	I am not in favor of the online class, for me, it's unfair. All of the students has the access to Google and other apps that can be used for cheating. We shouldn't tolerate this kind of action. What will they learn? How about after graduating and they don't know anything. I mean they adapt the wrong character and they might apply it to their work in the future as well. Apart from that, some of the teachers are not teaching properly, they give excuses and then leave us the module for the week, they do not teach but always give activities.
	Lessons are not really well-discussed. Some activities and quizzes are rated but does not justify the scores because the professor does not even tell the student about the student's mistakes.
	We can't perform actual activities like activities in the bar or hotel because it's online
	Most of the time, it's self-learning and not all students have equal grasp of the lesson so many gets left behind. The number of workload also force student to just finish the tasks instead of slowly and patiently learning and digesting the module.

• *Poor Assessment*

Assessment is one of the reference of student performance. Because of poor assessment students tend to complain of fair grading which eventually may led to poor competition among students since some students resort to cheating.

- *I am not in favor of the online class, for me, it's unfair. All of the students has the access to Google and other apps that can be used for cheating. We shouldn't tolerate this kind of action. What will they learn? How about after graduating and they don't know anything. I mean they adapt the wrong character and they might apply it to their work in the future as well. Apart from that, some of the teachers are not teaching properly, they give excuses and then leave us the module for the week, they do not teach but always give activities.*

These responses also imply that teachers are lacking instructions to students.

- *Lessons are not really well-discussed. Some activities and quizzes are rated but does not justify the scores because the professor does not even tell the student about the student's mistakes.*
- *We can't perform actual activities like activities in the bar or hotel because it's online.*

- *Most of the time, it's self-learning and not all students have equal grasp of the lesson so many gets left behind. The number of workload also force student to just finish the tasks instead of slowly and patiently learning and digesting the module.*

Table 15. Challenges of Students on Level of Acquired Knowledge and Skills Along Emotional State, Disappointment and Lack of Focus

Emotional State, Disappointment and Lack of Focus	I dont know
	None
	Walang masyadong naintindihan
	Very poor.
	For compliance
	Theories can be learned online. However, practical skills cannot be accurately measured in this mode of learning.
	My level of acquired knowledge was just moderate. I'm not that confident here. It's really hard to adopt the "new normal" thing and that makes me lutang most of the time during discussions.
	I barely learned anything this school year. Aside from the obvious struggles of online learning, only a few of our instructors are really determined to teach us.
	Some teachers are not teaching and keep on assigning students to report.
	Thou my profs are doing their part, I am really having a hard time to grasp our lessons now that we are in online.
	Procrastination is my enemy i think
	Sometimes I'm lazy to read the modules that's why Google saved me all the time

• *Emotional State, Disappointments and Lack of Focus*

Due to the interplay of the different challenges students are facing, students feel appointed on their acquired knowledge and skills. Some of the responses revealed that they are not certain of what they are learning anymore, some say they learned nothing, rated very poor and just attend classes for compliance.

- *I don't know*
- *None Very poor.*
- *For compliance*

Theories can be learned online. However, practical skills cannot be accurately measured in this mode of learning.

The above response imply that students agree that theories and concepts can be learned online but not on skills application and assessment.

- *My level of acquired knowledge was just moderate. I'm not that confident here. It's really hard to adopt the "new normal" thing and that makes me lutang most of the time during discussions.*
- *Though my profs are doing their part, I am really having a hard time to grasp our lessons now that we are in online.*

The above responses imply that they moderately learn on online classes which makes them stressed out during classes. Teachers' input is still wanting.

- *I barely learned anything this school year. Aside from the obvious struggles of online learning, only a few of our instructors are really determined to teach us.*
- *Some teachers are not teaching and keep on assigning students to report.*

The above responses imply that students feel frustrated because of teachers rely assigned topics to students instead them teaching. It is implied that students felt it when teachers do not show diligence among teachers who are expected to ensure learning among students.

- *Procrastination is my enemy I think.*
- *I lost my interest to study lately. It is becoming more difficult.*
- *Sometimes I'm lazy to read the modules that's why Google saved me all the time.*
- *I have many problems at home and school. I am confused whether to continue or not.*

It also implies that students are experiencing emotional or psychological problems.

Several psychological and emotional conditions can undermine students' motivation to get to class on time. Indeed, a hallmark symptom of conditions such as depression includes a decreased motivation to engage in normal daily activities. In

addition, prescription medications can interfere with motivation and may disrupt sleep patterns, which may indirectly affect students’ ability to overcome the challenges of online and distance learning.

Table 16. Challenges of Students on Level of Acquired Knowledge and Skills Along Negative Attitudes Towards Online and Distance Learning

Negative Attitudes towards Online and Distance Learning	I honestly cannot focus on studying because online modality or out of school learning for me is not suitable or the person like me that seek always guidance of teacher.
	Unlike face to face, you can ask the instructor what he is teaching that you do not understand and will understand better when taught in person.
	It’s hard to cope up with the online or distance learning since we have responsibilities in our home and knowledge given by the instructor virtually is not the same as given personally.

• *Negative Attitudes towards online and distance learning*

There has been an unquestionable upsurge in distance education in recent years. Between 2002 and 2011, the percentage of college students who were enrolled in at least one online course increased from 9.6% to 32% (Allen & Seaman 2013). Given this, it is extremely important to understand the experience of online courses from students’ perspectives. The ultimate beneficiaries of online education are, after all, the students. However under pandemic, the attitude of students towards online and distance learning has been shifted due to some other reasons.

- *Face to face classes is better than this so called online class. University and schools are very good environment than our house. Our home can be distracted sometimes. The level of acquired knowledge that I get is good but not quite. Relying solely on online education may hinder the holistic development of students and many may underperform later in their professional and personal lives.*
- *May natutunan naman kaso super unti unlike sa f2f, kasi ngayong online class nakakatamad talaga mag aral, ni hindi na nga ako ang rereview kasi open notes naman ang pweden naman mag search, tsaka sa dami ng gagawin sa bahay plus sa klase mas uunahin talaga yung sa bahay kesa sa school kaya naman izearch yung mga sagot, kayabat mo pa papahirapan sarili mo, and yun na nga gaya ng sinabi ko kanina internet connection and yung focus ng mga student yan din ang reason kaya unti lang naututunan.*
- *(I also learn but only a little, unlike in F2F, now in online classes I feel lazy to study. I don’t even review my notes since I can also research online. Since I have a lot of responsibilities at home, I make it as a priority so why so I have to attend classes where I can find answers online. So why do we have to make it difficult on our part. And just what I have mentioned poor internet connection and student focus are reasons why we learn a little.)*
- *I gave it a 4 because I think this online learning is not effective. Still learning lesson though is not the same and as better in face to face learning.*

The data implies that the students’ attitudes towards online and distance learning, affect their acceptance to knowledge and skills they want to develop. As one student, said:

- *Relying solely on online education may hinder the development of students and many may underperform later in their professional and personal live.*

This kind of negative perception may direct students’ participation to acquisition of knowledge and skills. Students are aware that f2f instructions will hone the holistic development of students.

Table 17. Challenges of Students on Level of Acquired Knowledge and Skills along Need for Teacher’s Input

Need for Teachers’ input	For me its ok to study online but the knowledge I acquired is not good because some teacher didn’t attend the google classroom.
	Although I can do a self-study, there were some topics that I couldn’t understand, like those topics that needs a visual instructions and computations.
	Actually when it comes to skills I can say that I don’t develop much because obviously the required skill in mycourse requires actual participation between the teachers and the students which this new mode of education can’t give.
	I’m having difficulty comprehending the lesson that our professor has assigned to us. To be honest, some professors simply upload the file and do not properly teach it. Since not all students are capable of learning itall through self-study, we demand professors who are dedicated and willing to teach students in any possible way they can
	In fact, I didn’t really get anything out of the lesson in this online class, maybe at first our teachers were strict withus in teaching and then later our teachers only provided activities through our virtual learning portal.
	It is difficult to study without the personal teaching of the instructor because we don’t get enough knowledge fromthem due to poor internet connection. As an IT student, I need instructor to teach me personally (face-to-face)
	because they will give me focus on explaining what I need to know.
	I don’t think so. There are also instances that it is hard to grasp understanding on a certain topic and it couldn’t be solve by just searching on Google. For me face to face instructions is still the best.
	Depende sa nagtuturo
	Kadalasan self study kapag hindi masyado napapa liwanag ng maayos ng guro ang lesson nila kasi minsan mahina yung signal
	It is hard to understand the terms which does not been discussed.
	Unlike face to face, you can ask the instructor what he is teaching that you do not understand and will understand better when taught in person.
	It is hard to understand the terms which does not been discussed.

• *Lack of teacher’s Input*

A familiar complaint, as demonstrated by Smart and Cappel (2006), is that online courses have heavy workloads requiring student autonomy and what students perceive to be a lack of instructor support. The following responses signifies their experiences with teachers along their level of acquisition of knowledge and skills.

- *For me its ok to study online but the knowledge I acquired is not good because some teacher didn’t attend the Google classroom.*
- *Actually when it comes to skills I can say that I don’t develop much because obviously the required skill in my course requires actual participation between the teachers and the students which this new mode of education can’t give.*
- *I’m having difficulty comprehending the lesson that our professor has assigned to us. To be honest, some professors simply upload the file and do not properly teach it.*
- *Since not all students are capable of learning it all through self-study, we demand professors who are dedicated and willing to teach students in any possible way they can*

The above response imply that teachers need to attend classes regularly. Students are expecting for learnings as they attend online classes. A strong student-teacher communication of required knowledge and skills shall be clearly discussed and mastered by students.

- *Although I can do a self-study, there were some topics that I couldn’t understand, like those topics that needs a visual instructions and computations.*

The response given imply that knowledge and skill cannot be learned alone by students without teacher intervention especially on topics that needs demonstrations and examples.

- *In fact, I didn’t really get anything out of the lesson in this online class, maybe at first our teachers were strict with us in teaching and then later our teachers only provided activities through our virtual learning portal.*

The above response imply that teachers eventually loss their interest to teach and is felt by students. This imply that teachers also loss motivation to teach for some factors.

- *It is difficult to study without the personal teaching of the instructor because we don't get enough knowledge from them due to poor internet connection. As an IT student, I need instructor to teach me personally (face-to-face) because they will give me focus on explaining what I need to know.*
- *I don't think so. There are also instances that it is hard to grasp understanding on a certain topic and it couldn't be solve by just searching on Google. For me face to face instructions is still the best.*
- *Unlike face to face, you can ask the instructor what he is teaching that you do not understand and will understand better when taught in person.*

The above responses suggest their interest to bring back face to face instruction, rather than online and distance learning. Students still want teachers' physical presence in addressing their difficulty in learning. Searching Google and other online library do not guarantee student learned knowledge. In order to develop their skills, teachers' inputs and actual demonstration are highly solicited.

B. Coping Mechanism of Students as to Challenges in Online and Distance Learning

This study also would like to determine the coping mechanism of students in the private and public SUCs in Camarines Sur. As the number of COVID-19 cases in the Philippines continues to rise, it is expected that emotions would run high, with the people of Luzon divided on how they will respond to the expanded community quarantine (ECQ) measures. According to studies, focusing on students can save lives by preventing too much stress, which can lead to depression, if we listen to our students' voices. (De Guzman, et al. 2020).

• **Digital Divide**

Digital divide is a term that refers to the gap between demographics and regions that have access to modern information and communications technology, and those that don't or have restricted access. This technology can include the telephone, television, personal computers and the Internet.

Table 18. Coping Mechanism of Students on Technological Constraint Along Digital Divide

Thematic Areas	Sub-Themes	Coping Mechanism	Sample Responses
Technological Constraint	Digital Divide	Extending support from others/classmates	Help those students who experienced difficulties
			Coping up by telling them to move themselves for we entered this together, then we'll end this together
			When we have classmates who encounter problems, we help them in the best way we can.
			Notify them or give information about the class link and schedule.
			We attend classes and encourages our classmates to attend as much as we can.
			We communicate frequently with each other ask them if they're ok or if they have a problem so that we can help
			I share to my classmates the important details I've learned.
I lead my classmates to attend the classes.			

In the following responses of students it is indicated that support system among students are highly initiated. Advantaged students extend hand to lead other disadvantaged students who are facing difficulties.

- *I lead my classmates to attend the classes.*
- *Help those students who experienced difficulties*
- *Coping up by telling them to move themselves for we entered this together, then we'll end this together*
- *We attend classes and encourages our classmates to attend as much as we can.*
- *We communicate frequently with each other ask them if they're ok or if they have a problem so that we can help*
- *Notify them or give information about the class link and schedule. I share to my classmates the important details I've learned.*
- *When we have classmates who encounter problems, we help them in the best way we can.*

The above response imply that students derive courage among each other in setting their goals or dreams. Students tend to encourage everyone to finish their studies despite of the challenges.

Fig 4. Level of Effectiveness of Coping Mechanism of Students Along Digital Divide

Among 1225 respondents, 527 or 44.3% experienced them effective 527 or 44.3% says it is effective, 148 or 12.5% perceived it very effective, while only 111 respondents or 9.1%, ineffective. It implies that the coping mechanism of students are generally effective.

➤ *Data Limit*

Data limit or data cap (bandwidth cap) is a service provider-imposed limit on the amount of data transferred by a user account at a specified level of throughput over a given time period, for a specified fee. The term applies to both home Internet service and mobile data plans.

Based on the findings among the coping mechanism of students along data limit are: sustaining resources/extra jobs, saving money/data, managing the usage of load, connecting with friends, family and neighbours, seeking financial help from family, outsourcing materials, switching internet provider.

Table 19. Coping Mechanism of Students on Technological Constraint Along Data Limit

Sub-Themes	Coping Mechanism	Sample Responses
Data Limit	Sustaining resources/extra jobs	I have some jobs to sustain my load.
		Good thing I have a part-time job to support my load needs whenever I run out of data package provided by the school.
		I grab the chance when there is a sideline job.
		We budget our allowance for our data packs, so it's fine also.
		The 50 pesos load has shareable GB data only and I had to make it last up to the 3rd day.
		I always check my data pack if its getting low so that I can plan on how can I download my modules effectively.
	Saving money/data	Saving money to provide for the online learning.
		I thrift my weekly load and used it in important matters, sometimes I didn't join in synchronous classes if I know I don't have enough load.
		Tinitipid ko ang data parabmakaabot sa isang linggo
		I always have data pack
	Managing the usage of load	I save my data right to last a month.
		Lessen the usage of data to the non-priority things
		I am now limiting my access to any social media platforms so that my data wouldn't get exhausted in this kind of stuff.
		Connecting to piso wifi.
	Connecting with friends, family and neighbors	Sometimes I attend class 30 mins only then another 30 mins for another class.
		I ask my friend If I can connect on their wifi
		I will go to my tito's house who have a wifi.
		I borrowed phone to my cousin to attend class whenever I don't have load or Wi-Fi connection
Seeking financial help from family	Reconnect with neighbor	
	I always seek help and financial support from my siblings so that I could still have enough data package for my classes.	
Outsourcing materials	I ask with my parents to give me a fund to have load subscription.	
	I opt to research another material which is related to the basis of the lesson.	
	I switch to a limitless internet provider such as Converge Fiber.	
Switching internet provider	I utilize postpaid wifi.	

It implies that students are exerting extra effort to sustain their data limit. Some students lookfor jobs to sustain their studies and family needs while other seek help from family. In order to value their resources, some practice saving and thriftiness. For those students who have limited resources connection wifi with friends, family and neighbor is another option. Switching to other service providers who offer limitless data was also practiced by students while outsourcing material was considered alternative to those research activities which requires heavy data usage.

Fig 5. Level Of Effectiveness of Coping Mechanism of Students Along Data Limit

As to effectiveness of these coping mechanism, 38% out of 1225 students rated these strategies effective, 16.3% rated it very effective while 10.7% rated it ineffective. It implies that there are students who are deeply challenged but fail to find meaningful strategies effective. One student responded:

➤ *I just let it happen. It is inevitable. I just attend classes when I have data.*

Table 20. Coping Mechanism of Students on Technological Constraint Along Poor Connectivity

Sub-Themes	Coping Mechanism	Sample Responses
Poor connectivity	Relocating	I will go to place that has a great signal
		I find a perfect spot where there is good internet connectivity
	Seeking help from others and informing instructors	Seek help to friends or classmates or letting my instructors informed.
		I talk to my classmates to send me their notes
	Switching to other service providers	I switched to converge fiber that has unlimited internet and a strong one too.
		"Connects with wifi or hotspots or use pisowifi
	Managing time to avail of strong internet signal	Gumigising ako ng maaga dhil ito ang oras na kadalasan malaks ang signal.
		I often do my school works at night up until early morning because that's when the connectivity is decent enough.
Start with Small, Fast Projects That Enhance Learning.		

Some of the responses revealed that common strategies of students to address poor connectivity are: relocating, seeking help from others and informing instructors, switching to other service providers, and managing time to avail of strong internet signal.

Based on the respondents relocating are common to students in coastal areas or areas with weak internet connectivity. In case there are classes, there are tendencies that student got late online or opted not to attend classes anymore. However, there are students who seek help to family and neighbourhood for a wifi connection. Sometimes, they text their classmate to inform their instructor that are experiencing poor connectivity so that they will be given some consideration. It can also be noted that there are students who avail of strong signal when accomplishing their modules and other class tasks. So hard for some students, they patiently wait for a strong signal, accomplish and submit their modules anytime of the day and night, the signal restores.

Fig 6. Level of Effectiveness of Coping Mechanism of Students along Poor Connectivity

Figure 6 shows the level of effectiveness of coping mechanism of students along poor connectivity. Out of 1225 respondents, 34.4% says these strategies are effective, 17.7%, very effective while 14.9% perceived it not effective. It implies that not all students avail of strong internet connectivity. There are students who are struggling to cope with poor connectivity issues.

In this study, learner’s Inefficiency is divided into learner’s indiscipline, unmotivated, and health issues/ strain/worsening health issues due to prolonged exposure to online classes. The data shows that the coping mechanism of students are: boosting self-discipline, attending class regularly, managing time, motivating oneself, inspiring others, setting priorities, goal-setting, and engaging leisure activities. It implies that in terms of discipline students impose themselves like waking up early and attending classes regularly:

- *I wake up early to not miss class*
- *Every time we will have synchronous discussion my classmates always attend the class.*
- *I avoid being absent and remember your goals for motivation to attend classes.*

Self-discipline is also manifested on how they manage their time by having their own schedule aware of and posted so that they will be reminded of their synchronous classes. It implies that in order to overcome learner’s inefficiency, imposing self-discipline is effective.

Whenever they feel unmotivated, students motivate themselves that they can survive all the challenges ahead.

- *Motivate myself that I can survive*
- *Try to do things that would motivate me or clear my mind.*

Table 21. Coping Mechanism of Students on Technological Constraint Along Learner’s Inefficiency

Thematic Areas	Sub-Themes	Coping Mechanism	Sample Responses
Learner’s Inefficiency	Indiscipline	Developing self-discipline	Strengthen self-discipline
			I wake up early to not miss class
			Every time we will have synchronous discussion my classmates always attend the class.
		Managing time	I avoid being absent and remember your goals for motivation to attend classes.
			Just manage the time.
			To cope up with attending classes, I set up my class schedule and determine which has a synchronous class
	Unmotivated	Motivating oneself	Make a schedule
			Motivating myself that I can.
			Motivate myself that I can survive
		Inspiring others	Try to do things that would motivate me or clear my mind.
			I tell them to continue and we will surpass those challenges.
			Motivate others to pursue classes
			Have some online games in between
			I am encouraging those students. Cause education is very helpful to our life.
			Encouraging them to attend class despite the challenges.
Health Issues/ Strain/Worsening Health Issues due to Prolonged online classes	Engaging Leisure activities	I cheer up and motivate my classmates	
		I prioritize subjects with deadline	
		Thinking of my dreams.	
			Exercise before classes.
			schedule time for using phone
			I do some recreational activities
			I wake up early and exercise

In order to influence others, inspiring their classmates to pursue their education is also a way to help others to surpass all the challenges which includes goal setting and priorities:

- *I tell them to continue and we will surpass those challenges.Motivate others to pursue classes.*
- *I am encouraging those students. Cause education is very helpful to our life.*
- *Encouraging them to attend class despite the challenges.*
- *I cheer up and motivate my classmatesThinking of my dreams.*

Along health issues/ strain/worsening health issues due to prolonged online classes, engaging leisure activities and exercising before classes are also some of their options.

- *Schedule time for using phone.*
- *I do some recreational activities.I wake up early and exercise.*

Fig 7. Level of Effectiveness of Coping Mechanism of Students Along Learner’s Inefficiency

Figure 7 shows the level of effectiveness of coping mechanism of students along poor learner’s inefficiency, out of 1,225 respondents, 32.2% affirms it is effective while 11% says it’s very effective. while 21.1% replied ineffective. It implies that learner’s efficiency is influenced by their self-discipline,time management, motivating oneself, inspiring others, setting priorities and goal setting.

➤ *Initial Support by Teachers*

Many countries around the world stopped schools, colleges, and institutions in reaction to the COVID-19 problem in order to stop the virus from spreading. According to UNESCO data, the peak in school closures occurred in early April 2020, affecting almost 1.6 billion students in 194 countries, amounting for more than 90% of total enrolled students (UNESCO, 2020). Because of the sudden closure of schools, education policymakers, school principals, and instructors had to develop online and distance learning mode to ensure that students are protected without sacrificing the education they deserve.

Thus, many systems have embraced online teaching (and learning) on a massive scale, frequently in conjunction with widely available remote learning materials.

Locally, the pandemic has radically altered the Philippines' higher education system, with a noticeable shift in online training as a means of limiting the virus's spread. Many teachers and students were concerned about the sudden shift to online learning because a big portion of the population has unreliable internet access and few technological devices (Pastor, 2020, Maradilla-Santos, 2016). Since the pandemic started and presently shows little signs of declining, worries whether internet connection would not suffice to support online education persist as a challenge (Lapitan, et al, 2021).

Table 22. Initial Support extended by Instructor by Communicating, Giving Guidance and Assistance

Initial Support	Sample Responses
Communicating with students	They find way to connect us
	They give feedback and assessment of our performance.
Giving guidance/ assistance	Please guide us more and be patient if sometimes we can't pass the activity on time
	Guide us to how access the materials.
	Sending some instructions about the apps we aren't familiar with.
	Teacher always reminded us our learning activities to be submitted and when we wants to clarify some things they will answer as they go online.

The responses revealed that most teachers regularly communicate with students. Some of them give guidance and assistance in developing the value of patience, accessing materials, internet application and learning activities. They are also guided as to the deadlines while some queries are addressed during online classes.

Another support extended by teachers is providing students with learning materials like module, social media/flexi kits for those who cannot access the internet or no gadget at all. They also provide recorded video lecture or recorded meeting so that those students who failed to attend classes can catch up the lesson. Some institution gives student to rent a brand new wifi and gadget if those are unavailable to them.

Table 23 Initial Support extended by Teachers by Providing Materials and Recorded Lectures

Providing materials and recorded lectures	Teachers will provides modular teaching for those students who don't have a computer or cellphone
	They provide other social media/ or flexi kit method for the students
	They record the lessons online then send it to our gc for the students who did not attend to learn and atleast know the lessons and assignment
	They provide video lecture
	If the student can't download some file on google classroom, teachers made a modules to give on the students who wasn't able to access the assessments
	Our institution enables the student to rent a brand new wifi and gadget if those are unavailable to us.

Another support given by teachers is giving special consideration to students with special attention. Teachers are lenient enough to consider the pandemic situation. Some students are given consideration as to deadlines for those students with poor internet connectivity and no gadget.

Consultations and motivational talks are also given to address the concerns of students, especially coping the situation and challenges of online and distance learning.

Table 24. Initial Support Extended by Teachers by Giving Special Considerations and Catering the Needs of Individual Students.

Giving considerations to students	The teachers have always consideration.They understand the difficulties in online learnings
	Our professors offer a chance to send a physical module pack for the students who cannot attend online classes so that they aren't left behind.
	Teachers are very considerate and address the concerns of students
	They provide time to answers questions and one of my instructors would always tell us to write down our activities on a clean sheet of paper in case we don't have computers.
Considering student backgroundand needs	Our professors divide the class into modular learners and online learners. There are consultations with modular learners and online learners but those modular learners are also allowed to attend online classes if possible.
	Provide an equal access to all students, considering the minorities of having no internet or lack of devices. Giving
	Students a convenient approach to deliver lessons and tasks.
	After the session ends some of our instructors, they tried to send their recorded video class discussion because they know not every one of his/her student have a good internet connectivity.
	They encourage us to survive online classes through motivational talks.
	They are giving us advices that it is not all about those who have advantages but it is all about giving us the effort and our best to surpass the challenge with the online classes.

➤ *Initial Support by Parents*

The first issue that has developed is that online learning is only available to a select group of pupils who have access to a high-speed broadband connection at home. While network operators have mostly succeeded in maintaining services and efficiently utilizing pre-existing capacity during lockdown periods (OECD, 2020), there are still geographical locations and populations where this is not the case.

In order to provide information and guidance to parents on successful strategies for supporting their children's learning, education systems should strive to strengthen engagement between schools and parents. Teachers, on the other hand, require assistance in incorporating technology effectively into their teaching practices and approaches, as well as in assisting students in overcoming some of the challenges that come with it.

Imposing discipline and providing guidance and moral support to their children are most important in these trying times. Although some parents are strict enough to let them study harder, manage time and develop patience considering that teachers are also doing their part. Parents aims were to develop them into a better, more focused person and make sure that students performance are just enough to justify their effort for excellence, so as not to distress them.

Table 25. Initial Support Extended by Parents by Providing Discipline, Guidance and Moral Support

Imposing discipline, and providing guidance and moral support	They tell that I should do my best and be disciplined enough.
	Giving us knowledge to become a better person and to become a person who has discipline.
	Teach us to be patient and manage their time properly
	Whatever the result as long as I did my best I think they will be satisfied.
	They always teach and guide us to be well-mannered.
	They sometimes telling me that to focus more because the teachers are trying their best as well.
	Give guidance and moral support.

As provider of child’s education, parents’ financial support are expected to them. Most of the parents bought them gadget like android mobile phones and laptop. They add regular as part of their daily and weekly expenses. Some parents also help their students by assisting them some queries in which they fail to ask from teachers. Aside from emotional and financial support, some of them assist their children on technical side, in finding stronger internet access.

Table 26. Initial Support Extended by Parents by Giving Financial Support and Assistance on Queries and Difficult Classroom Tasks

Financial support	Last semester, they bought me Gadgets and laptop
	Giving allowance for a weekly load
	Buying modem that can be registered when the wifi is not working
Giving assistance on queries and difficult classroom tasks	The initial support given by my parents is that they give me time for the activity and sometimes I will also ask them questions for lessons.
	They always give advice and additional information
	My mom tries to help me have better access to the internet
	They shares some we ask on them what's the meaning of this what's the meaning of that

Space and good learning environment are crucial to student’s concentration during online classes. In this study, one of the challenges mentioned by respondents are errand and household chores which hinder them to be early and miss online classes. However, some of the initial support extended by parents is providing space between school task and household chores through scheduling.

Table 27. Initial Support Extended by Parents by Providing Space and Good Learning Environment

Providing space between school task and household chores	Binibigyan ako ng oras pata matapos ang gawing sa klase bago anggawaing bahay (My parent give me time to finish first all my school tasks before those household chores done.)
	They gave me time and don't disturb in time of studying.
Provide good learning environment	They lessen the noise that will affect me from studying.
	Helping me to cope with this kind of interruption.
	Send us to place where there's a good signal
	My father made a little table and I organized my things before starting.

Finally, parents’ goal setting, encouragement, motivation and follow up are also helpful support to students. In this trying times, some students are losing motivation to continue schooling because of the different burdens. However parents support, encouragement and motivation help students to develop their confidence and positive thinking. Constant follow-up are also conducted by asking teachers of their performance and assessment, giving feedback, including health issues since students are due to prolonged exposure to radiation during online classes.

Table 28. Initial Support Extended by Teachers by Goal Setting and Giving Encouragement and Motivation

Goal-setting	Helping me to realize that I have dreams.
	Guide and help me in the best way they can to achieve my dreams
Giving encouragement and motivation	They tell us to don't give up always trust yourself
	Motivating me to always come in class.
	They always tell us to reach for our dreams
	Give us encouragement that we can do this and we can always go on
	They cheer up us
	They give words of encouragement to be patient
Giving follow up	Give an advice to more patient.
	Always checks if i have everything I need in online classes
	They check if their children already pass their assessment
	Kinukumusta nila kami especially the guidance if may concern or what sa online class
	They calling us using cp if may problem sa school or any concerns.
	They are giving there feedbacks
	We always check if they have that health issues

➤ *Student Preferences in Online and Distance Learning*

As the demand for online learning has grown, some researchers have directed their efforts toward better understanding the characteristics and perspectives of online learners (Kirbey, et al , 2016).

Fig 8. Student Preferences in Online and Distance Learning

Students who have a favourable assessment of their online experiences are more likely to enroll in additional online courses, according to previous study (Dobbs, Waid, & del Carmen, 2009; Stewart, Waight, Norwood, & Ezell, 2004). Student opinions of online courses that require them to reflect on their experiences have produced mixed outcomes in studies. Research has also repeatedly demonstrated that students are most frequently drawn to online learning options for reasons of convenience, flexibility, and course availability (Bocchi, Eastman, & Swift, 2004; Kirby, Sharpe, Bourgeois, & Greene, 2010).

Student opinions of online courses that require them to reflect on their experiences have produced mixed outcomes in studies. While easier scheduling, a variable learning speed, a wide range of courses, and better computer proficiency are all considered benefits, communication and technological difficulties, as well as minimal or no personal interaction with students, are some of the most often mentioned drawbacks (Dobbs et al., 2009; Kirby, Sharpe, Bourgeois, & Greene, 2010; Lofstrom & Nevgi, 2007).

Table 29. Students' Preference on Online and Distance Learning

Indicators	WMn	Verbal Interpretation
I prefer my online courses as they are very structured with set due dates similar to face-to-face courses	2.46	Slightly Agree
Online classes help me comprehend the course materials compared to Classroom learning.	2.49	Slightly Agree
Online environment makes it easier for me to communicate with my instructor than classroom environment	2.21	Slightly Agree
I am more comfortable responding to questions by email than orally	2.47	Slightly Agree
My technical skills (email/internet apps) has increased since attending online classes	2.81	Agree
I spend more time on my homework in comparison with regular classroom learning	2.40	Slightly Agree
Instructor understands the online environment and makes it easy to learn.	2.65	Agree
I develop my sense of self-discipline and responsibility.	2.61	Agree
I prefer online and distance learning since I encounter less constraints than traditional classes	2.40	Slightly Agree
I can accomplish and send my task faster than regular classes.	2.22	Slightly Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.79- Strongly disagree; 1.80-2.59- Slightly agree; 2.60-3.19- Agree; 3.20-4.00- Strongly agree

It can be gleaned from the data that students technical skills (email/internet apps) has increased and developed their sense of self-discipline and responsibility since they attended online classes.

Meanwhile they also preferred online and distance learning since instructor understands the online environment and makes it easy to learn. On the other hand all other indicators revealed that student- respondents slightly agree that online courses are very structured with set due dates similar to face-to-face courses; online classes help me comprehend the course materials compared to classroom learning; Online environment makes it easier to communicate with my instructor than classroom environment; More comfortable responding to questions by email than orally; can spend more time to do homework in comparison with regular classroom learning; and online and distance learning encounter less constraints than traditional classes.

It implies that students' preference in online and distance learning is very low. Their level of satisfaction is weak due to the challenges they encountered and their struggle to cope with the situations given from their responses. One of the major challenges among students is the poor internet connectivity and their capability to sustain their resources with the aid of their parents. Issues with broadband connectivity in remote locations make it difficult for students to take advantage of online learning opportunities (Aiswaryab, AdityaaGirish, Jhaa, 2020). Because many board courses are practical, switching totally to online mode may not be practicable, necessitating the creation of a hybrid mode.

CHEPTER FIVE CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that there are an interplay of different challenges of students which affects their preference in online and distance learning. This is also reflected on their attendance and punctuality in online classes. Major causes of students' challenges are poor internet connectivity, teachers' factor and learner's inefficiency. Although most of them, are struggling with this new style of learning, students also applied varied coping mechanism strategies to overcome these challenges. It can be concluded that support from teachers and parents are important in these trying times. College students still needs teachers' input to enhance their knowledge and develop their skills. Meanwhile, their level of satisfaction on online and distance learning is found moderately weak.

RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that these identified challenges may serve as input in designing online curriculum and alternative program for students facing difficulty in online and distance learning. In terms of poor internet connectivity, the institution shall devise internet assistance programs that would cater their students' needs and difficulties in cooperation with the local government unit and other funding agencies. Dissemination of learning materials may be intensified however, while developing the value of social and professional responsibility and embracing the new normal among students is essential. Students may be given series of orientation before online class started. A clear classroom policy may be reflected in the syllabus and may be revisited based on the background of students. Set expectations explicit and have the consequences flexible and specific in order to develop students' sense of discipline. Classroom management may also be adjusted to this new style of learning without sacrificing the causes for continual absenteeism and drop outs. Communication and support system may be extended with leniency but the gap between traditional face to face instruction preferences to online and distance learning may be bridged.

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